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Towards quantitative partial discharge simulations

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Abstract

This paper computationally investigates partial discharges (PDs) in the form of self-sustained gas discharges. It presents two methods for predictive modeling: (1) a new low-fidelity algorithm for the PD inception voltage is introduced. The method is volume-resolved and describes both the strength of the self-sustained Townsend mechanism as well as the conventional streamer (or bulk) mechanism. It also intrinsically computes the inception region, i.e. the region where a first electron also leads to a discharge. (2) We apply a high-fidelity plasma model based on kinetic Monte Carlo, which self-consistently resolves the plasma dynamics during the PD process. The two models are complementary in the sense that the low-fidelity model provides the when and where the PD occurs, while the high-fidelity model resolves the PD process itself, starting from the first electron. Prediction and quantification of the PD processes is provided for four application cases: (1) protrusion-plane gaps, (2) spherical voids, (3) twisted wire pairs, and (4) triple junctions. Validation of the low-fidelity method is done through comparison with published experiments (where available), as well as virtual verification through comparison with the high-fidelity plasma model.

Keywords: partial discharge, streamer, simulation, townsend discharge

1. Introduction

Prediction of the partial discharge (PD) inception voltage in gases is foundational to virtually all high-voltage (HV) equipment as well as many plasma-based applications such as CO₂ conversion [1–4], combustion [5–10], catalysis [11–16], and medicine [17]. PDs always begin with an initial electron that accelerates in an electric field, and which ionizes the gas when its kinetic energy exceeds the ionization potential of the gas. The secondary electrons released in the ionizing collision undergo the same process, such that the number of free electrons and conductivity of the gas increases exponentially. This process occurs over a length scale $1/\bar{\alpha}$ where $\bar{\alpha} = \bar{\alpha}(E/N)$ is

the effective ionization coefficient in the gas, E is the electric field, and N is the number density of neutral molecules. The field corresponding to $\bar{\alpha} = 0$ is called the *critical field* E_{cr} , and $\bar{\alpha} > 0$ is a necessary—but not sufficient—requirement for partial breakdown. Partial discharges can take many forms, such as negative glows, Trichel pulses [18], and streamer discharges [19, 20]. While PDs are beneficial to many plasma based applications, they are undesirable in others. For example, PDs in HV equipment are considered destructive as they can deteriorate insulating media (both gas and solid) over time, and are often tantamount to equipment failure.

1.1. PD inception mechanisms

There are two disparate inception mechanisms that can be considered as pure forms of PD. The first is the *self-sustained Townsend discharge*, where feedback from cathodes is responsible for igniting the gas discharge. Here, remnant positive ions from the ionization process drift to the cathode and cause secondary electron emission with an efficiency

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γ_i , a process which then cascades. For historical reasons, $\bar{\alpha}$ is termed the first Townsend ionization coefficient and γ_i is called the second Townsend ionization coefficient. Note that secondary electron emission from ions is not the only feedback mechanism at the cathode; secondary electrons can also occur due to photoemission, bombardment with excited molecules, and through field emission.

The textbook derivation of the self-sustained Townsend mechanism considers a uniform gap of length d and a gas with an effective ionization coefficient $\bar{\alpha}$, where a single initiatory electron at the cathode grows into an avalanche of $e^{\bar{\alpha}d} - 1$ secondary electron-ion pairs. When the positive ions strike the cathode they release $\gamma_i(e^{\bar{\alpha}d} - 1)$ new starting electrons on average, and the PD inception voltage (PDIV) is then implicitly given by the solution to

$$\gamma_i (e^{\bar{\alpha}d} - 1) = 1. \quad (1)$$

This is the well-known Paschen law, whose conventional form can be obtained by substituting $\bar{\alpha} = Ape^{-Bp/E}$ and solving for the voltage $V = Ed$, where A and B are constants, and p is the absolute pressure.

The other inception mechanism is the *streamer mechanism*. Dating back to the works by [19, 21, 22], the streamer mechanism is based on the number of electrons required for modifying the field in which electron avalanches develop. More specifically, streamers evolve due to accumulation of space charges, which enhance the electric field at the front of the avalanche and facilitates further discharge growth. The main distinction between the Townsend and streamer mechanisms is the separation into feedback from cathode surfaces (Townsend) or the gas volume (streamer). The streamer threshold is conventionally represented as

$$\int_l \bar{\alpha} dl \geq K_c, \quad (2)$$

where e^{K_c} is the number of electrons required for modifying the background field. By convention, K_c is usually called the streamer constant. For discharges in atmospheric air, a common range of values used for K_c is 18–21 according to [19] and [21]. The physics of the avalanche-to-streamer transition is, however, not completely transparent as it is the *spatial distribution* and not the *number* of electron-ion pairs that matter. We will briefly discuss the current state-of-the-art regarding this point in section 2.3.

Various communities also have a markedly different interpretation of equation (2). The HV community normally interprets equation (2) as a pure streamer criterion, i.e. with a value of K_c that indicates the presence of single-avalanche space-charge modifications of the electric field. However, positive coronas have been measured down to $K_c = 8 - 9$ [23], and space charge effects are minor, if not negligible, at these values of K_c . The resolution to this paradox is that such low values of K_c are possible due to photoionization feedback [24] that leads to multiple electron avalanches that cumulatively modify the electric field and then launches a streamer. Equation (2) is thus not a pure streamer criterion, but rather a corona criterion where feedback from the gas volume is responsible

for the cascading avalanches (and eventually also the space-charge modified field) [24]. The usage of equation (2) to predict streamers is therefore a bit misleading. In order to properly distinguish which two mechanisms we discriminate between, we will simply distinguish between these two by referring to equation (1) as a *cathode feedback mechanism*. Equation (2) will be referred to as a *bulk feedback mechanism*, with the implicit understanding that K_c is not the critical size of an electron avalanche, but rather a parameter that describes when feedback effects from the bulk gas leads to discharge ignition. For the sake of completeness, we note that this feedback can be either due to photoionization feedback responsible for positive corona ignition, or due to space-charge modified fields arising from a single electron avalanche (i.e. a direct avalanche-to-streamer transition).

The cathode and bulk feedback mechanisms are based on two seemingly disjoint criteria, although they physically represent two extremes of a continuum under which some physical processes can be ignored for one mechanism but not the other. However, both mechanisms may clearly be simultaneously present. Both initiation mechanisms also require a suitably placed initial electron, which can come either from the gas or from cathode surfaces. Equations (1) and (2) do not provide this region. Hence, these equations only provide the PDIV threshold and not the PD inception probability, which also requires a quantitative description of the statistical time lag (see e.g. [25]). However, for sufficiently long voltage applications the waiting time for a first electron is less important, and equations (1) and (2) are then believed to be sufficiently accurate for predicting the PDIV.

In most geometries, the measured PDIV at positive and negative polarity are different. For example, in protrusion-plane gaps with a live protrusion and grounded plane, the PDIV at negative polarity is normally lower than for positive polarity. The physical explanation for this lies at the electrode: at negative polarity, impinging positive ions (and photons) cause secondary electron emission from the cathode, and the discharge can then evolve as a self-sustained Townsend discharge. For a positive voltage application, however, the first detectable PDs at positive polarity in such configurations occur due to photoionization feedback from the gas, which often lead to the formation of positive streamers. Because the feedback mechanisms are different, the PDIV at positive and negative voltage applications are also inherently different.

Currently, the most widely used model for PDIV prediction is due to [26], whose model is restricted to pure streamer-type PDs with the PDIV threshold given implicitly by equation (2). A review of the assumptions subsequently made in this model was recently presented as well as criticized by [27]. Indeed, adoption of only equation (2) in any PD model will *a priori* dismiss all cathode feedback processes, such as prediction of negative glows and Trichel pulses. Ultimately, this may degrade the model's predictive capabilities in cases where the PD evolves due to cathode feedback rather than bulk feedback.

High-fidelity descriptions of PDs based on plasma modeling are also becoming increasingly common. These models self-consistently solve for the evolution of the plasma and ion densities together with the electric field. While these models

are numerically much more expensive than models based on equations (1) and (2), they also provide unique insight into the dynamic behavior of the plasma. Moreover, these models do not artificially segregate between cathode and bulk feedback mechanisms, since these two extremes are emergent phenomena of the plasma model. Such models can be based on particle-in-cell models [28], fluid models [29], or with hybrid models [30, 31]. Approaches for correcting the inadequacy of the local field approximation (LFA) in the electron impact ionization source term have also been reported [32], and can be used for stabilizing the behavior of fluid models for cathode-streamer interactions [33]. Plasma-based PD modeling has been used to study streamer formation near sharp points [28, 34], in gas-filled voids [35], and in bubbles [36]. Other studies have focused on Trichel pulse formation [37–39] near sharp points.

1.2. Contents of this paper

Equations (1) and (2) have been successful in predicting the PDIV across many applications, but fail to provide the following:

- The volumetric region where initial electrons also lead to discharges. While this point is less important for long voltage applications, i.e. where the statistical time lag is much shorter than the voltage pulse duration, it is exceedingly important when the time lag and voltage pulse application have similar time scales.
- A quantitative description of the subsequent discharge phase, as only the PDIV can be calculated.

In this paper we present steps toward improved quantitative modeling of the PD process. We begin by considering a new low-fidelity algorithm in which the cathode and bulk feedback mechanisms are simultaneously resolved in space, incorporating all possible positions of the first electron. The main goal of this algorithm is to unify and simplify the PDIV prediction using low-cost computer calculations, with a focus on three specific points:

- (i) Volumetrically resolve both mechanisms for arbitrary field configurations.
- (ii) Automatic differentiation between the two mechanisms, i.e. separate prediction of both the cathode feedback PDIV (U_T) and the bulk feedback PDIV (U_K).
- (iii) Resolve the so-called critical volumes and critical surfaces for both mechanisms, with potential future extensions to probabilistic PD inception models that incorporate evaluations of the first electron availability.

Recently, [40] presented a volumetric model of equation (2) in arbitrary field configurations, with a focus on automatic calculation of the critical volume and the streamer inception probability. The latter is defined by the probability that a first electron appears inside the critical volume, which greatly simplifies the probabilistic formulation of streamer inception. In this paper we add the cathode feedback mechanism into the

same formulation, with an overall aim of unifying the PDIV prediction of the two mechanisms into a single algorithm. Although probabilistic formulations for transient voltages is possible [40], this paper focuses on the formulation only for static voltages.

In a second step, we use a high-fidelity model based on kinetic Monte Carlo (KMC) [41] where we track the discharge process dynamically. Unlike the low-fidelity model, the high-fidelity model is capable of following the discharge path with full incorporation of discharge stochasticity, with simultaneous inclusion of both cathode and bulk feedback mechanisms. While the low-fidelity model is used to predict the PDIV, the high-fidelity model is used to quantitatively describe the PD process itself. This model is presented in section 3 and has been used to explore the dynamics of streamer discharges [34, 41, 42] in the past. In this paper we apply the model to studies of PD inception in the form of self-sustained Townsend discharges, i.e. we primarily investigate PD evolution where cathode feedback dominates over bulk feedback.

The outline of this paper is as follows: We first present the outline of the low-fidelity model (which we call a KT-model) in section 2. The high-fidelity model [41] is briefly summarized in section 3, and this model is also used for virtual verification of the KT-model where experimental results are not available. Application examples are then given in section 4, with an emphasis on evolving discharges in various geometries:

- (i) Protrusion-plane gaps (section 4.1).
- (ii) Spherical voids (section 4.2).
- (iii) Contacting wire pairs (section 4.3).
- (iv) Triple junctions (section 4.4).

Note that all of our calculations examine PD inception in inhomogeneous field configurations. Finally, this paper is briefly summarized and concluded in section 5.

2. Low-fidelity model (KT-model)

The low-fidelity model is conceptually simple and based on the volume-reconstructed electron avalanche integral used by [40]. An electron that appears at some position \mathbf{x} will on average evolve into an avalanche of $e^{K(\mathbf{x})}$ electrons where

$$K(\mathbf{x}) = \int_{\mathbf{x}}^{\text{Until } \bar{\alpha} \leq 0} \bar{\alpha}(E) dl. \quad (3)$$

This integration follows the electron path, i.e. backwards along the electric field line passing through \mathbf{x} . The termination criterion for the avalanche is here given as $\bar{\alpha} \leq 0$, but we also assume that avalanches stop growing when they hit a surface.

Figure 1 shows the underlying concept of the particle algorithm that we use for volumetrically calculating equation (3), where an electrostatic solution for the electric field $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x})$ is assumed to have already been calculated. Computational electrons are then seeded in all grid cells where $\bar{\alpha}(\mathbf{x}) > 0$, and a Lagrangian particle code is then used to numerically resolve the electron avalanches starting from

Figure 1. Concept sketch of the KT-model for a simple geometry with an anode at the top and a cathode at the bottom, together with two conceptual positions of the starting electron. The regions bounded by dashed lines indicates the ionization regions. The red-shaded regions are regions where electron avalanches are too small for starting electrons to cause discharge feedback. The blue-shaded regions show the part of the ionization region where bulk feedback (e.g. avalanche-to-streamer) is possible, while the green regions shows the part of the ionization region where cathode feedback can initiate discharges.

initial positions \mathbf{x} . This integration runs anti-parallel to \mathbf{E} . The trapezoidal rule is used to calculate $K(\mathbf{x})$ as defined by equation (3) [40], which provides us with a volume-resolved value for $K(\mathbf{x})$.

2.1. Ion-induced secondary emission

In addition to the K -value, we introduce a new value $T = T(\mathbf{x})$ which describes the strength of the self-sustained Townsend discharge mechanism, occurring due to feedback at cathode surfaces (metallic or dielectric). This value is derived from $K(\mathbf{x})$ as follows: an electron seeded at position \mathbf{x} will generate $e^{K(\mathbf{x})} - 1$ secondary ions which move opposite to the electrons, i.e. along the electric field line passing through \mathbf{x} . This field line will strike a cathode surface and we obtain the second Townsend ionization coefficient γ_i at the point where the field line intersects the cathode surface. Notationally, we represent this as $\gamma(\mathbf{x})$, which is to be understood as the second Townsend coefficient at the material position where a field line passing through \mathbf{x} terminates. Furthermore, if the field line passing through \mathbf{x} also passes through a region where $\bar{\alpha} \leq 0$ before reaching the cathode, we set $T(\mathbf{x}) = 0$ for the initiatory position \mathbf{x} . The T -value is then set to

$$T(\mathbf{x}) = \gamma(\mathbf{x}) \left(e^{K(\mathbf{x})} - 1 \right). \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) describes the strength of the self-sustained Townsend discharge, and is a simple multi-dimensional formulation of equation (1). If $T(\mathbf{x}) > 1$ for an initial electron

appearing at position \mathbf{x} , then the discharge is self-sustained due to feedback from the cathode.

2.2. PDIV calculation

Equations (3) and (4) are volumetric formulations of the conventional cathode and bulk feedback mechanisms, formulated for arbitrary field configurations and all positions of the first electron. Note that there is an inherent difficulty in determining the onset of gas discharges due to bulk feedback since the threshold value on $K(\mathbf{x})$ that actually leads to a self-sustained discharge is non-trivial to compute. We discuss this point in more detail in section 2.3. The formulations for $K(\mathbf{x})$ and $T(\mathbf{x})$ contain the same physics as the formulations in equations (2) and (1), but are formulated volumetrically such that the regions where first electrons also lead to PD inception are directly available. In particular, $T(\mathbf{x})$ is essentially just Paschen's law for a first electron appearing at position \mathbf{x} , evaluated along the field line passing through that position. Thus, regions $T(\mathbf{x}) > 1$ indicate regions where a first electron appearing at position \mathbf{x} lead to a self-sustained Townsend discharge. Likewise, regions $K(\mathbf{x}) > K_c$ indicate regions where the first electron leads to initiation of a PD due to bulk feedback. Although this segregation into completely separate discharge types is fundamentally misleading (both types are part of a continuum), it is useful for quickly determining whether cathode feedback or bulk feedback is the dominant ignition mechanism. Discharge inception is equivalent to fulfilment of either of

$$\max_{\forall \mathbf{x}} K(\mathbf{x}) > K_c, \quad (5)$$

$$\max_{\forall \mathbf{x}} T(\mathbf{x}) > 1. \quad (6)$$

As with the conventional formulations in equations (1) and (2), the criteria are implicitly formulated and also nonlinearly dependent on the applied voltage U . One simple way of finding the lowest possible voltage that fulfills the inception criteria is to obtain $K(\mathbf{x})$ and $T(\mathbf{x})$ for a range of voltages $U \in [U_1, U_2, \dots]$ and check for the lowest voltage where one of the above criteria are met. Because space-charge effects are negligible during the avalanche, $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x})$ only needs to be obtained once, and fields at higher or lower voltages can be obtained through linear scaling. Notationally, we write these values as $K(\mathbf{x}; U)$ and $T(\mathbf{x}; U)$. More precisely, if we consider a threshold value K_c and K -value calculations for various applied voltages U as $K(\mathbf{x}; U)$, we first search for voltages U_i and $U_{i+1} > U_i$ in each position \mathbf{x} that bracket K_c , i.e. $K(\mathbf{x}; U_i) \leq K_c$ and $K(\mathbf{x}; U_{i+1}) > K_c$. The PDIV due to bulk feedback from a first electron at \mathbf{x} is then interpolated as

$$U_K(\mathbf{x}) = U_i + \frac{(U_{i+1} - U_i) [K_c - K(\mathbf{x}; U_i)]}{K(\mathbf{x}; U_{i+1}) - K(\mathbf{x}; U_i)}. \quad (7)$$

The equivalent procedure for cathode feedback is

$$U_T(\mathbf{x}) = U_i + \frac{(U_{i+1} - U_i) [1 - T(\mathbf{x}; U_i)]}{T(\mathbf{x}; U_{i+1}) - T(\mathbf{x}; U_i)}, \quad (8)$$

where i is such that that $T(\mathbf{x}; U_i) \leq 1$ and $T(\mathbf{x}; U_{i+1}) > 1$. These two expressions define the lowest possible PDIV for initiating a discharge due a first electron appearing at position \mathbf{x} . The lowest possible voltages for initiating these processes are $U_T = \min_{\mathbf{x}} U_T(\mathbf{x})$ and $U_K = \min_{\mathbf{x}} U_K(\mathbf{x})$, whereas the minimum inception voltage regardless of process is

$$U_I = \min \left[\min_{\mathbf{x}} U_T(\mathbf{x}), \min_{\mathbf{x}} U_K(\mathbf{x}) \right]. \quad (9)$$

Inception at this voltage requires an optimally placed initial electron. This position, which we term \mathbf{x}_I , simply corresponds to the value of \mathbf{x} where either $\min_{\mathbf{x}} U_T(\mathbf{x})$ or $\min_{\mathbf{x}} U_K(\mathbf{x})$ has a global minimum.

For the PDIV prediction, the T -value is as useful as the threshold value K_c . The condition $T(\mathbf{x}) > 1$ can be rewritten as

$$K(\mathbf{x}) > \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{\gamma(\mathbf{x})} \right), \quad (10)$$

which has an obvious functional form similar to $K(\mathbf{x}) > K_c$. However, $T(\mathbf{x}) = 1$ can lead to a lower PDIV than $K(\mathbf{x}) = K_c$. E.g., with $\gamma = 10^{-3}$ one obtains a cathode feedback PD condition $\max_{\mathbf{x}} K(\mathbf{x}) \gtrsim 6.9$, whereas bulk feedback thresholds are usually reported as $K \geq 9 - 10$ [23] or greater. The self-sustained cathode feedback criterion is also rather insensitive to changes in $\gamma(\mathbf{x})$ since it enters logarithmically. In section 4.2 we show that when γ changes by one decade from 10^{-2} to 10^{-3} , the PDIV due to cathode feedback increases by only 16%.

2.3. Model uncertainties

The mathematical representation of the self-sustained cathode and bulk feedback mechanisms are subject to substantial simplifications. E.g., the feedback process at the cathode is at best only approximately described. Firstly, the electrons in the avalanche spread out as the avalanche grows, and this natural spread is therefore also inherited by the positive ions as they drift back towards the cathode. The ions need to strike the cathode on surface regions where $E > E_{cr}$ in order to initiate new electron avalanches. However, because the diffusive spread of the avalanche is not accounted for, the model will overpredict the number of ions initiating new avalanches on the cathode. To the best of our knowledge, this process has been evaluated as a corrective factor for the required avalanche size for initiating streamer discharges [43], but not for self-sustained Townsend discharges. Montijn and Ebert [43] have derived the avalanche-to-streamer transition distance, and shown that it depends on both the applied electric field and the electron diffusion. Their derivation assumes evolution in a uniform background field E , with the solution for the avalanche-to-streamer transition distance d given implicitly by the solution to

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\alpha}d - \ln(\bar{\alpha}d) + \ln \frac{F(1) - F\left(1 + \sqrt{\frac{\mu E}{4D\bar{\alpha}(\bar{\alpha}d)}}\right)}{F(1)} \\ = \ln \frac{16\pi k}{F(1)} - \ln \frac{\mu e \bar{\alpha}}{D\epsilon_0}, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where e is the unit charge, μ is the electron mobility, D is the electron diffusion coefficient, and $F(x)$ is given by

$$F(x) = \frac{\operatorname{erf}x}{x^2} - \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}x} \exp(-x^2). \quad (12)$$

Equation (11) describes the distance d under which a single initial electron develops into an avalanche that perturbs the background field by a factor k . [43] suggest that $k=0.03$ is a sufficiently accurate value for the transition distance.

Figure 2 shows the solution to equation (11) for air at standard atmospheric pressure and temperature. Details regarding the parameterization of the electron transport coefficients ($\bar{\alpha}$, μ , and D) as functions of E/N are given in section 4. The number of electrons is given by $\exp(\bar{\alpha}d)$, so that a larger number of electrons is therefore required in order to modify the field at lower background fields. As discussed by [43], this is due to the fact that at lower fields the formative time of the avalanche-to-streamer transition is longer, and the diffusive spread of the electrons is therefore also greater. These corrections are not a part of the KT-model as the avalanches are assumed to propagate only along field lines.

Another clear point of uncertainty regards the selection of a threshold value K_c . In the KT-model we have simply set the criterion to $K(\mathbf{x}) > K_c$ where K_c is (for simplicity) set to a constant value. Although this criterion is often used to describe the onset of positive streamers, the formulation is not physically complete as K_c is not truly a constant and depends on both the photoionization level and the discharge geometry. The role of photoionization in the initiation of a positive corona (or streamer) is well known (see, e.g. [24, 44, 45]). Indeed, the photoionization feedback region and by extension also the PDIV can be calculated for very simple geometries. Unfortunately, calculation of the required geometric factors for geometries of practical engineering interest become substantially more difficult, and this is a problem that we have not yet dealt with.

Incorporating a quantitative description of photoemission feedback is, unfortunately, substantially complicated. It requires complete excitation cross-sections for the gas, radiative lifetimes for the relevant excited molecular states, pre-dissociation and pressure-dependent quenching rates, and wavelength-dependent secondary emission probabilities for the cathode material. A hefty compilation of this process is available for the conventional photoionization mechanism in air [46] (in the 98-102 nm range), but not for the broader UV spectrum down to typical work functions of 3–5 eV that are relevant for secondary electron emission from metals and polymers. Alternatively, one may lump photoemission processes into an empirical correction factor for $\gamma(\mathbf{x})$. For PDs in dielectric wedge-shaped gaps, [47] derived such an effective secondary Townsend coefficient at the cathode. Because of the substantial difficulties faced in predicting the production of secondary electron emission-capable photons, as well as efficiently calculating the photon distribution in general geometries, we do not pursue the role of photoemission in the KT-model further. Nonetheless, lumping multiple processes into an effective second Townsend ionization coefficient $\gamma(\mathbf{x})$ (as

Figure 2. Solution to the avalanche-to-streamer transition criterion given by [43]. The line corresponding to $\bar{\alpha}d$ is plotted against the left axis and the avalanche-to-streamer transition distance d is plotted against the right axis.

is done in [47] and other papers) is possible, but requires that the model is subsequently fit to experiments.

3. High-fidelity model ($\hat{\text{Ito}}$ -KMC)

The high-fidelity model is based on a particle representation of the conventional drift-diffusion approximation for plasma discharges [41]. Electrons and ions in this model obey a microscopic drift-diffusion process ($\hat{\text{Ito}}$ process)

$$d\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{V}dt + \sqrt{2D}dN, \quad (13)$$

where $\mathbf{X}(t)$ is the particle position, and \mathbf{V} and D are the drift velocity and diffusion coefficient. N is a random number sampled from a normal distribution with a mean value of zero and a standard deviation of one, and we close the velocity relation in the LFA as $\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{v}_e(\mathbf{X})$, $D = D_e(\mathbf{X})$. Here, $\mathbf{v}_e = -\mu_e \mathbf{E}$ is the fluid drift velocity where μ_e is the electron mobility and D_e is the electron diffusion coefficient. This model is physically similar to a conventional macroscopic drift-diffusion model, except that electrons are treated as particles rather than as a fluid. As in [41], reactions are resolved stochastically by using a KMC algorithm. Due to these features, the model is called an $\hat{\text{Ito}}$ -KMC model, but it is essentially just a particle-based drift-diffusion-reaction model for the electrons and ions.

Unlike the simplified static breakdown model, the high-fidelity model self-consistently solves for the electric field using

$$\nabla \cdot (\epsilon_r \mathbf{E}) = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0}, \quad (14)$$

where ρ is the space charge and ϵ_r is the relative permittivity of the materials. Charge conservation and associated boundary conditions are also enforced on surfaces [41, 48]. Note that incorporation of a statistical time-lag in the $\hat{\text{Ito}}$ -KMC model is intrinsic to the model since the simulation starts from specified initial electrons at time t .

As the $\hat{\text{Ito}}$ -KMC model resolves the discharge from the first electron, secondary electron emission, photoionization, electron diffusion, and reactive stochasticity are emergent phenomena. Thus, while the KT-model requires a grossly simplified model for cathode feedback and can only empirically describe bulk feedback, the $\hat{\text{Ito}}$ -KMC model can resolve this coupling intrinsically by stochastically evaluating whether or not the photons and ions produced in the avalanche phase cause ionization in the gas or emission at the cathode. Further details regarding the model and its association with conventional fluid drift-diffusion models are given in [41].

4. Application examples

The KT and $\hat{\text{Ito}}$ -KMC models have been implemented into the chombo-discharge [49] framework, which we have used for streamer simulations in the past [34, 48, 50–54]. The framework includes efficient solvers, adaptive mesh refinement, and also supports parallel calculations.

Below, we consider four application examples where we apply the two methodologies. For brevity, we consider a simple reaction scheme for air at standard atmospheric pressure and temperature. We track the electrons and the following ion types: N_2^+ , O_2^+ , and O^- . Electron transport data (e.g. the ionization coefficient $\bar{\alpha}$) is calculated using BOLSIG+ [55] with cross sections from the Phelps database [56]. The same transport coefficients for the electrons are used in the KT and $\hat{\text{Ito}}$ -KMC models. The critical field in our calculations is $E_{\text{cr}} = 2.9 \text{ kV mm}^{-1}$. The ion mobility is set to $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^{-2} (\text{V s}^{-1})$ and the ion diffusion coefficients are calculated using the Einstein relation. We use the same second Townsend ionization coefficient γ for both N_2^+ and O_2^+ , which is set to $\gamma = 10^{-3}$ (we vary this value in section 4.2). We consider a simplified reaction set for the $\hat{\text{Ito}}$ -KMC calculations:

as well as a photoionization-producing reaction following the Zheleznyak model [52, 57]. All the low-fidelity calculations are initiated by first calculating the background field $\nabla \cdot (\epsilon_r \mathbf{E}) = 0$, using $K_c = 15$ for all examples. We include experimental values in the application examples wherever they are available.

The time step in the computer simulations was restricted by a Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy (CFL)-like condition on the particles according to

$$\Delta t = \frac{2\Delta x}{\max(|V_x|, |V_y|, |V_z|)}. \quad (18)$$

The above time step is computed for all computational particles. We also include a hardcap on the time step such that Δt can not decrease below 10 ps.

Figure 3. Setup for the protrusion simulations. The radius of the needle protrusion is $500\ \mu\text{m}$ and the tip radius is $200\ \mu\text{m}$. The opening angle of the needle tip is 30° . All domain faces in the simulation are grounded, with the exception of the upper face where we apply a homogeneous Neumann condition $\partial_n \Phi = 0$. The needle tip is at live voltage U , and the secondary emission coefficient on the cathode is set to 10^{-3} .

4.1. Example I: Protrusion-plane gap

In this example we consider negative PDs in the protrusion-plane gap shown in figure 3. Geometries like this are typically used when experimentally determining the PDIV for gases, for studying negative corona discharges [58], or used as a proxy for protrusion-type defects in HV equipment. As mentioned in section 1.1, negative PDs in these geometries usually start in the form of self-sustained Townsend discharges at a lower applied voltage than positive PDs.

First, we run the KT-model and calculate the K and T values for both polarities. Figure 4 shows the results of this calculation, where figures 4(a)–(d) show the calculated values at applied voltages $U = \pm 5\ \text{kV}$. In the figures we use a superscript (\pm) to indicate the voltage polarity. Figures 4(a) and (b) show the calculations for negative polarity, and figures 4(c) and (d) show the calculations for positive polarity. We observe from figures 4(b) and (d) that Townsend discharges are only possible when the needle electrode is at negative polarity, i.e. $T^+ = 0$ everywhere when the needle is at positive polarity. Figures 4(a) and (c) also show that the electron avalanching regions are qualitatively and quantitatively different. At negative polarity the largest avalanches are produced by electrons that begin close to the cathode surface. At positive polarity, electrons that begin close to the anode do not generate much ionization before leaving through the anode, so $K(x)$ is always zero on the anode surface. The largest avalanches are instead produced by electrons that start at the edge of the ionization region. Recently, [40] studied how the availability of negative ions inside these regions influences the inception probability of streamer discharges.

Figure 4(e) shows the maximum K and T values as a function of the applied voltage U at negative polarity. The inception voltages are indicated by U_T and U_K and are calculated following the interpolation procedure in section 2.2. We find

Figure 4. KT-model calculations for the protrusion-plane geometry. Figures (a)–(d) show the calculated K and T values in a plane passing through $y=0$. The applied voltage is $U = \pm 5\ \text{kV}$, and the superscript indicates the voltage polarity. Figure (e) shows the maximum K and T values calculated with the protrusion at negative polarity in the voltage range $U = 2\text{--}6\ \text{kV}$.

that the inception voltage for self-sustained Townsend discharges is $U_T = -4.3\ \text{kV}$ whereas bulk feedback yields $U_K = \pm 5.8\ \text{kV}$.

Next, we run a computer simulation of the PD inception process using the $\hat{\text{I}}\text{to-KMC}$ model at an applied voltage $U = -5\ \text{kV}$, i.e. $U_T < U < U_K$ such that the discharge dynamics are driven by ion bombardment of the cathode. The computer simulation is initiated by placing approximately 500 electrons within a $200\ \mu\text{m}$ radius sphere centered at the cathode tip (see figure 3). We used multiple first electrons in order to ensure that at least some of the electrons fell within a region in which $T(x) > 1$, and did not stochastically attach early in the discharge process.

Figure 5 shows snapshots of the electrons, N_2^+ ions, and O^- ions during the initial stage of the discharge process. First,

Figure 5. Left panel: free electrons at various time steps. Middle panel: N₂⁺ ions. Right panel: O⁻ ions. All particles are colored by their velocity as indicated in the top row (color ranges are truncated for easier visualization of fast/slow particles).

we see from $t = 5$ ns that the initial electrons grow into a larger avalanche, and that this initial stage leaves behind remnant N_2^+ ions near the cathode. The N_2^+ ions are only produced relatively close to the cathode in this simulation since the width of the ionization zone is only around $350 \mu\text{m}$ at $U = -5$ kV (e.g. see the outer edge for the K -value in figure 4(c)). Several photoionization events also occur during the initial PD formation, which are indicated for the electrons at $t = 10$ ns, where we can also see that the electron distribution is depleted in the region between the initial avalanche and the cathode. Between 10 ns and 20 ns, additional starting electrons have been generated through ion bombardment of the cathode (by either N_2^+ or O_2^+), which have led to new avalanches. One such avalanche is indicated in figure 5 for the electrons at $t = 20$ ns. This process then repeats itself, such that additional electron–ion pairs are consistently generated in the ionization zone ahead of the cathode.

The ionization and secondary electron emission processes in figure 5 lead to charge separation of electron–ion pairs. Positive ions are generated only within the ionization zone and drift relatively slowly towards the cathode, while the more rapid electrons escape the ionization zone and form a diffuse cloud of electrons that extend outward from the cathode. As the electrode is charged negatively, the charge separation enhances the electric field between the electrode and the positive ions, and correspondingly also reduces the field between the positive ions and the electrons.

Figure 6(a) shows the peak electric field and the total positive and negative charge in the gap. The early stage of the evolution is characterized by intermittent space-charge buildup, while after approximately 110 ns we observe a very sharp rise in the ionization activity and maximum field stress. This ionization activity spike lasts for around 5–10 ns before gradually decaying, and it temporally coincides with the onset of a space-charge modified field. We have illustrated this field reshaping in figures 6(b)–(g) where we show the field magnitude and space charge density. The space charge density is shown on a truncated color scale in order to distinctively illustrate positively and negatively charged regions, as is the field stress which is clamped to values $\leq 15 \text{ kV mm}^{-1}$. In figures 6(d) and (e) we observe the formation of a sheath region on the cathode with a high electric field which exceeds 40 kV mm^{-1} . In front of the sheath we observe a corresponding low-field region. The actual formation of the sheath region is relatively fast, and fully forms in about 5–10 ns. After the sheath has formed, the Townsend discharge process recedes, which we see from figure 6(a) where the positive charge begins to decay after approximately 125 ns. We point out that the amount of negative charge in the gap still increases slowly throughout the simulation since secondary electrons are still being released from the cathode due to ion bombardment, but on average more ions are lost to the cathode than what are being generated through electron impact ionization.

In a recent review, [33] presented a thorough overview of the current understanding of negative coronas with an emphasis on Trichel pulses. The sharp rise in ionization activity, as seen in figure 6(a), was suggested to be due to

the formation of a positive streamer that propagates towards the cathode. In the terminology by [33] the usage of the term ‘streamer’ is not the same as the originally proposed single-avalanche streamer mechanism [19, 21, 22]. Rather, their usage of the term also includes field screening from cumulative electron avalanches, similar to how equation (2) is interpreted in the context of bulk feedback in the ignition of positive coronas. Our computer simulation displays, to a large degree, consistency with the suggestions by [33]. For brevity, some clarifications are nonetheless necessary: first, positive streamers—in the conventional understanding—propagate due to provision of seed electrons in front of them, which are provided through photoionization, at least in air [57] and in CO_2 [34, 59]. Note that seed electrons in the form of background ionization can lead to morphological changes in the streamer, see [60]. Second, such positive streamers screen their interior, and this screening occurs due to a positive space charge layer that surrounds a quasi-neutral channel. In figures 6(d)–(e), there is indeed an ionization front moving towards the cathode, where the field close to the cathode increases while the field decreases further out. This ionization front initiates due to a space-charge modified field from distinct clouds of positive and negative charge rather than a space charge *layer*. It is only when the ionization front approaches the cathode that it leaves behind a space charge layer. We show this in figure 7 which shows the same data as the space charge data shown in figures 6(d)–(f). One other notable difference from filamentary streamer channels is that we do not observe large regions of quasi-neutrality. Finally, in the computer simulation the seed electrons that feeds the ionization wave moving towards the cathode tip are also due to secondary emission from the cathode rather than photoionization (which is the main mechanism for filamentary positive streamers).

4.2. Example II: spherical voids

In this section we consider a 3D spherical void in a solid insulator, as shown in figure 8 where all geometrical and material parameters are defined. In HV equipment, such voids often become critical defects in, e.g. GIS spacers, cable joints, or cable insulation. Discharges in spherical voids have previously been modeled by [36] and [35], but the PDs in these studies are single-avalanche streamers rather than self-sustained Townsend discharges. Here, we focus on the latter type of discharge. We perform two types of calculations: 1) compute the PDIVs with the KT-model, using various selections of γ in order to illustrate the role of cathode feedback. 2) A direct simulation of the PD evolution using the Îto-KMC model.

Figure 9(c) shows the KT-model predictions for the PDIVs as a function of γ . We observe that $U_T < U_K$ over a wide range of γ -coefficients for this geometry, so the discharge type at the lowest possible inception voltage is a self-sustained Townsend discharge. Figures 9(a) and (b) show the K and T -values for $U = 15$ kV and $\gamma = 10^{-3}$. The maximum values of $K(\mathbf{x})$ and $T(\mathbf{x})$ are found for electrons that initiate from the lower void surface since this maximizes the length over which the electron avalanches grow.

Figure 6. Simulation data for the Îto-KMC model in the protrusion-plane gap. (a) Maximum electric field and free charge (positive and negative) as a function of time. (b)–(g) Electric field magnitudes and space charge densities sliced through a plane passing through $y=0$ (i.e. through the center of the needle cathode). The space charge density is shown on a truncated color scale in order to more easily discern positively and negatively charged regions.

We next investigate the PD evolution using the high-fidelity model with $U = 15$ kV and γ -values of 10^{-3} and 10^{-5} . The PDIV calculations in figure 9(c) predict that a self-sustained

Townsend discharge will develop for $\gamma = 10^{-3}$ but not for $\gamma = 10^{-5}$. The simulations are initiated by seeding five initial electrons $1 \mu\text{m}$ away from the lower void surface. These

Figure 7. Same data as in figures 6(d)–(f), but showing the space charge layer on the cathode on a different color scale.

Figure 8. Setup for the void discharge simulations. The upper face of the simulation cube is at live voltage U and the lower face is grounded. The inside of the void is air-filled ($p = 1$ bar) and the void surface is assigned a constant value γ .

Figure 9. (a) and (b) Discharge values $K(x)$ and $T(x)$ (shown as a slice through the plane $y=0$) using $\gamma = 10^{-3}$ for an applied voltage $U = 15$ kV. The solid line inside the void for the $T(x)$ plot shows the contour $T=1$, which is the bounding surface of the region where an initial electron also leads to a self-sustained Townsend discharge (i.e. the critical Townsend volume). The initial electrons in the Íto-KMC calculations were seeded within this volume. (c) Model predictions for PDIV thresholds as a function of the second Townsend ionization coefficient γ .

electrons drift upward in the void and ionize the gas, generating downward-drifting secondary ions (N_2^+ and O_2^+) that then initiate the Townsend PD.

Figure 10 shows the evolution of the N_2^+ ion distribution for $\gamma = 10^{-3}$ and $\gamma = 10^{-5}$. The discharge process is first characterized by initial ionization from the starting electrons, which leave behind a trail of positive ions in their wake, indicated as primary avalanches in figure 10. Because the positive ions are generated by electron impact and the electron avalanche broadens diffusively, the positive ion trail inherits the width of the electron avalanche. The characteristic diffusion length of the avalanche at the top of void given by $\sqrt{2D\tau}$ where D is the electron diffusion coefficient and τ is the transit time of the electrons across the void. At the conditions in figure 10 we have $E \approx 10$ kV mm^{-1} , $D \approx 0.21$ $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$, and $\tau \approx 0.3$ ns, such that the characteristic diffusive width of the avalanche is approximately $12 \mu\text{m}$. At higher fields the diffusive broadening of the avalanche would be smaller since the transit time τ would be shorter. The next phase of the PD evolution is characterized by downward drift of these ions, as seen in figure 10

for $t = 15$ ns. For $\gamma = 10^{-3}$ these ions cause new starting electrons due to secondary emission from the cathode side, which result in the secondary avalanche shown for $t = 20$ ns. No analogous feature is seen for $\gamma = 10^{-5}$ due to the low probability of secondary electron emission, and the ions simply drift to the lower side of the void without initiating cathode feedback, and the discharge then terminates. However, for $\gamma = 10^{-3}$ the ions from the primary avalanche releases new starting electrons from the cathode side. We have indicated these subsequent avalanches as secondary and tertiary avalanches in figure 10. The electrons in these avalanches rapidly impinge on the upper side of the void, while the ions drift more slowly to the lower side. Negative charge therefore rapidly deposits on the upper side while an equivalent amount of positive charge accumulates more slowly on the lower side.

In a later phase of the evolution, accumulation of space and surface charge from the PD screens the electric field. Figure 11 shows the evolution of the electric field and surface charge density in a plane passing through the center of the void. As the avalanches grow upwards and the electrons are much faster than the ions, the field screening first occurs near the top of the void. The initial screening seen for $t = 50$ ns is therefore due to negative surface charge (from impinging electrons) and the remnant positive space charge in the form of N_2^+ and O_2^+ . This screening is visually reminiscent of the space-charge screening in streamer channels, although it here occurs due to cumulative charge separation from multiple Townsend avalanches and not from a space charge layer. A conceptually similarly screened field region appears at the lower region in the void at later times due to drift of positive ions towards the bottom of the void, which can be seen for $t \geq 200$ ns in figure 11. We point out that although the surface charge distribution is bipolar, it is not symmetric and the spread of the positive surface charge distribution is greater than the negative one. This occurs because the width of the negative surface charge distribution in the void is primarily determined by the diffusion of the electron avalanches as they grow upward, see e.g. figure 10(a). The positive spread is thus determined by the diffusive spread of the electron avalanches as they grow upward and the diffusion of the positive ions as they transit to the lower side of the void.

A long-standing narrative suggested by [26] is that the residual field in the void after a streamer PD is equal to the critical field required to sustain a positive or negative streamer. This conjecture was criticized by [35] who in detail showed that when the self-consistent PD problem is solved using plasma models, the field does not relax to the streamer stability field. As we will show, the [26] conjecture is also incorrect for the Townsend discharge where there are no streamers. Physically, one expects that the Townsend PD decays when the surface and space-charge modified field reduces the Townsend criterion to $T(x) < 1$ everywhere (i.e. no critical cathode feedback). This condition is implicit in the Íto-KMC model where the evolution occurs self-consistently, but is not contained in the KT-model since the surface and space charge distributions are not known *a priori*.

In order to illustrate that the residual field in the Townsend PD is not equal to the streamer stability field, figure 12 shows

Figure 10. Evolution of the N_2^+ ion distribution in a spherical void with $\gamma = 10^{-3}$ and $\gamma = 10^{-5}$ using the $\hat{\text{Ito}}$ -KMC model.

Figure 11. Field screening and PD decay of the Townsend process ($U = 15$ kV, $\gamma = 10^{-3}$). The data shows the electric field magnitude in the center of the void, and the encircling line shows the surface charge density. The bottom row shows the field and surface charge density in the left panel and the N_2^+ ion distribution the right panel.

the calculations of the KT-model using a synthetic dipolar surface charge distribution (parameters are given in the figure caption). In figure 12, surface charges screen the field to yield $T(\mathbf{x}) < 1$ everywhere, and cathode feedback is therefore non-critical. However, the electric field exceeds E_{cr} by a factor of 2–3 everywhere inside the void, which is substantially higher than the streamer stability field in air, normally estimated at 20%–40% of E_{cr} . Returning to the high-fidelity calculation in figure 11, feedback becomes $T(\mathbf{x}) < 1$ already around 150 ns, but at this point in the evolution the void is still filled with many positive ions and a residual field $E > E_{cr}$ (see figures 10 and 11). Correspondingly, although cathode feedback recedes, positive ions continue to bombard the lower surface of the void, which releases secondary ionizing electrons. $T(\mathbf{x}) < 1$ thus marks the slow and steady decline of the PD, but the relatively large amount of ionic space charge in the void still causes secondary emission and thus also increases the surface charge further. The terminal surface charge is therefore higher than

Figure 12. KT-model for the void with pre-existing surface charge $\sigma(\theta) = \sigma_0 \sin^7 \theta$ where θ is the polar angle of the void. The calculation uses $U = 15$ kV, $\gamma = 10^{-3}$, and $\sigma_0 = -200$ pC mm $^{-2}$. The total (positive charge) in the void is approximately 1.3 pC. The color-coded data shows the indicated values at the center of the void, i.e. through the plane passing through $y = 0$. Left: T -values. Right: field magnitude E .

Figure 13. Setup for the contacting wire PD simulations.

one simply yielding the condition $T(\mathbf{x}) < 1$. The main implication of this evaluation is that determination of the residual surface charge requires knowledge of the dynamically evolving ionic space charge in the PD event, quantities which are only available in high-fidelity plasma models.

4.3. Example III: contacting wire pairs

In this example we consider PD inception for contacting, insulated wires with conductor radius r and insulation thickness $\Delta = s - r$, see figure 13 where all parameters are defined. This geometry is representative of the turn-to-turn insulation in electric motors. Recently, [47] derived an analytic model for the PDIV in quasi-uniform gaps with application to precisely such geometries. Here, we consider application of the KT and $\hat{\text{Ito}}$ -KMC models for this geometry. All calculations for this geometry are done in Cartesian 2D such that the depth of the discharge is not resolved.

Figure 14. (a) and (b) Discharge values $K(x)$ and $T(x)$ using $\epsilon_r = 5$ ($\Delta/\epsilon_r = 20$) for an applied voltage $U = 1.4$ kV. The figure shows a closeup of the small gap between the two wires shown in figure 13. We have also indicated the inception point x_I at the lowest possible Townsend PDIV. (c) Predicted PDIV thresholds as a function of the reduced insulation thickness Δ/ϵ_r .

Figures 14(a) and (b) show the calculated K and T values in the small gap between the two wires. Figure 14(c) shows the calculated PDIVs as a function of Δ/ϵ_r where $\Delta = s - r = 100 \mu\text{m}$ and $\epsilon_r \in [2, 20]$. Calculated values are included for both $\gamma = 10^{-3}$ and $\gamma = 2 \times 10^{-3}$, which are compared against the experimental data from [61–65], which was compiled by [47]. The KT-model here predicts a lower onset for self-sustained Townsend PDs than for bulk feedback, and also reproduces the available experimental data quite well over a comparatively large range of Δ/ϵ_r . We point out that at even lower values of Δ/ϵ_r , field emission might become non-negligible which ultimately leads to a departure from Paschen’s law. [47] has demonstrated that this regime is reasonably well-described by the modified Paschen law [66], and has also included an improved parametrization of γ that incorporates field and photo-emission.

Next, we simulate a PD event for the wire–wire geometry with the Ito-KMC model, using $\epsilon_r = 5$, i.e. $\Delta/\epsilon_r = 20 \mu\text{m}$. The simulation was initiated by seeding the region surrounding the contacting wires with a few initial electrons. The applied

Figure 15. Temporal evolution of the N_2^+ ion density (color map), surface charge density (colored line) for a Townsend PD between two insulated wires. The second Townsend ionization coefficient is set to 10^{-3} and the voltage difference between the two wires in the simulation is $U = 1.4$ kV.

voltage is $U = 1.4$ kV, which is approximately 200 V above the Townsend PDIV and 500 V below the streamer PDIV (see figure 14(c)).

Figure 15 shows the dynamic evolution of the N_2^+ ion density and surface charge density near the wedge-like gap in the region where the two wires touch. The KT and Ito-KMC predictions of the inception point and voltage (indicated in figure 14) are in agreement, and the discharge indeed initiates at the location predicted by the KT-model. The actual gap distance between the insulating dielectrics where the discharge

Figure 16. Cross-sectional and side views of the triple junction geometry. We use a second Townsend coefficient $\gamma = 10^{-3}$ on both the insulator and electrode surfaces.

initiates is around $40\text{--}45\ \mu\text{m}$, which also agrees quantitatively with the analytic model predictions by [47] (see figure 6 in [47]). Although we do not show the field distribution explicitly, the $\hat{\text{I}}\text{to-KMC}$ calculation shows that the discharge is indeed of the Townsend type and no characteristic features of streamers (e.g. space charge layers) were seen in the computer simulation. Rather, the growth of the discharge is characterized by multiple avalanches that form between the two dielectric surfaces and the charge distribution virtually consists only of surface charge and positive space charge in the form of rather slow-moving residual N_2^+ and O_2^+ ions. As the avalanches grow upward towards the anode wire, negative charge (from electrons) deposits at the top surface while positive charge from N_2^+ and O_2^+ deposits more slowly on the lower surface, as seen in figure 15 for $t \geq 100\ \text{ns}$. Eventually, and in complete analogy with the void simulation presented in section 4.2, the deposited surface charge eventually screens the field and the discharge growth recedes.

4.4. Example IV: triple junction

In this example we consider a model for a triple junction (a gas-electrode-dielectric interface), as seen in figure 16 where all geometric parameters are defined. The geometry consists of a dielectric shaft with a hexagonal cross-section which protrudes through a ring electrode. This is a representation of a mechanical feedthrough in a medium voltage switchgear. Here, the ring electrode represents a part of a gasket and the hexagonal shaft is a mechanical switch designed to rotate in order to position, e.g. earthing switches. When the inner ring radius approaches the effective radius of the shaft, six individual triple points emerge where the two parts contact, and these points are then nuclei for PDs.

A 3D view of the triple junction geometry is shown in figure 17, which also shows the field stress on the boundary for an inner ring radius of $r = 17.51\ \text{mm}$, i.e. with a minimum gap distance of $10\ \mu\text{m}$ between the electrode and the insulator. The length of the dielectric shaft in this geometry is 4 cm, whereas the length of the ring electrode is 1 cm. We have

Figure 17. Field stress on the surface for the triple junction geometry with $U = 30\ \text{kV}$ and $r = 17.51\ \text{mm}$.

used a curvature of $500\ \mu\text{m}$ on the electrode edges (both inner and outer) and a curvature of $100\ \mu\text{m}$ on the hexagonal shaft edges.

First, we calculate the PDIVs for this geometry as a function of the electrode inner radius, keeping all the other geometrical and material parameters fixed. Figure 18(c) shows the calculated inception voltages when we vary the distance between the insulator and electrode from $5\ \mu\text{m}$ to $1.28\ \text{mm}$. We find that the Townsend mechanism is the dimensioning PD mechanism for this setup, and also that there is a minimum PDIV for the two processes which does *not* occur when the two materials touch (i.e. for an ideal triple junction). Rather, the minimum Townsend PDIV is approximately 20 kV and occurs for a separation distance of $40\ \mu\text{m}$. Likewise, the minimum bulk feedback PDIV is approximately 30 kV and occurs for a separation distance of $80\ \mu\text{m}$. Conceptually, both minima can be interpreted as analogs of the Paschen curve minimum. As the gap distance between the insulator and electrode decreases the electric field in the gap correspondingly increases, but the available space over which the avalanches can develop simultaneously decreases.

Figures 18(a) and (b) show the PDIVs on the insulator surface when the electrode is at positive polarity. The color-coded data shown in the figures is to be interpreted as the minimum voltage required for a first electron on the surface to evolve into a PD, as given by equations (8) and (7). As discussed earlier in the paper, this data is a volumetric variable, but is shown here on the surfaces only.

Next, we simulate a PD event for this setup using the $\hat{\text{I}}\text{to-KMC}$ model. We consider the worst-case scenario with $r = 1.754\ \text{mm}$, corresponding to a gap distance of $40\ \mu\text{m}$. This value corresponds to the minimum Townsend discharge PDIV in figure 18(c). The applied voltage is set to $U = 28\ \text{kV}$, which is approximately 8 kV above the Townsend discharge PDIV and 2 kV below the bulk feedback PDIV. We initiate the simulation by seeding a few electrons in the gap near the triple

Figure 18. PD inception voltages for the triple junction geometry. (a) Predicted U_K with positive polarity at the electrode. (b) Predicted U_T with positive polarity at the electrode. The triple junction gap distance is 0.04 mm in figures (b) and (c). (c) PDIVs as a function of the gap distance between the insulator and electrode.

point shown in figure 18(b). No seed electrons are placed in the other triple junctions so that only a single PD occurs in the computer simulation.

Figure 19 shows the PD evolution as snapshots at various time instants indicated in each frame. Here, we show the electric field strength both on the surface (left column) and in a planar slice passing through the triple junction (middle column). The right column shows the O_2^+ ions, which are generated through electron impact ionization and photoionization. The initial electrons that were used to seed the PD event are shown in the left column for $t = 0$ ns. Since the electrode is at positive voltage, the electrons drift toward the conductor and generate secondary electron-ion pairs that then initiate the self-sustained Townsend discharge.

The initiation point of the PD in $\hat{I}to$ -KMC calculation is in agreement with the predictions of the KT-model, which predict that PD initiates from the curved edge of the conductor. We point out that the discharge does not initiate in the region with the highest field stress, which is found in the gap between the electrode and the insulator. The evolution of the PD itself occurs in analogy with the other examples presented in this paper. First, the initial electron avalanches grow toward the electrode, producing secondary ions that drift toward the insulator. When these ions neutralize at the insulator, they release new starting electrons with an efficiency $\gamma = 10^{-3}$ and also leave behind a positive surface charge. The secondary electrons evolve as separate avalanches that grow toward the

conductor, and the process then cascades. Because the avalanche size is largest closest to the anode (where the avalanche distance is largest), most space charge is produced close to the anode. The electrons are much faster than the positive ions and quickly neutralized at the anode, and only positive space charge is left behind in the triple junction gap. Because both the anode and the space charge consist of positive charge, the residual ions shield the anode. We have indicated this initial shielding region in figure 19 with a symbol A. In effect, when this region forms the effective avalanche length is smaller, and there is a corresponding reduction in the size of the electron avalanches that initiate from the insulator. Eventually, the remaining positive space charge in the form of N_2^+ and O_2^+ ions drifts toward the insulator surface and neutralize. Similar to the $\hat{I}to$ -KMC simulations in sections 4.2 and 4.3, this leads to further screening of the electric field and eventually also the termination of the PD.

5. Conclusions

5.1. Summary

We have presented a new PD inception model (KT) for the PDIV prediction, which is fundamentally just a volumetric representation of the conventional Townsend and streamer criteria. However, this algorithm discriminates between the two inception modes (cathode feedback and bulk feedback), and provides a volumetric view of the discharge initiation regions. It is also valid for arbitrary field configurations, and relatively performant with run-times of a couple of minutes. Incorporation of pre-existing space or surface charges, e.g. for prediction of the PD extinction voltage, is therefore naturally supported. We have also presented the application of a recently developed high-fidelity model ($\hat{I}to$ -KMC) to various PD studies. The low- and high-fidelity models are complementary in the sense that the KT-model predicts the PDIV and the $\hat{I}to$ -KMC predicts the dynamic PD evolution. Four application examples were included in this paper: protrusion-plane gaps, a spherical void, contacting wire pairs, and triple junctions. In all cases we compared the KT and $\hat{I}to$ -KMC models at otherwise identical conditions, and we found mutual consistency between the two.

5.2. Outlook

For the KT-model, extension to a transient, probabilistic formulation seems feasible, following the approach by [40]. In this case the incorporation of a statistical time-lag enters naturally due to the explicit formulation of the first-electron source [40]. While the KT-model can be used as a black-box model, one should note that the model remains fundamentally simplified. For example, diffusion corrections of the electron avalanches and ions are not incorporated, nor is the role of photoemission. In this paper the KT-model was formulated as a volume problem, but the numerical integration of the model still occurred along field lines. It is not uncommon for e.g. HV engineers to only use field lines when evaluating

Figure 19. Triple junction PD evolution process. Left column: field strength E on the conductor and insulator surfaces. Middle column: field strength E through a planar slice passing through the center of the triple junction. Right column: O_2^+ ions, colored by their velocity.

the streamer inception criterion. Polarity-dependent calculations of both $K(\mathbf{x})$ and $T(\mathbf{x})$ along selected field lines is still possible, but the critical regions $K(\mathbf{x}) > K_c$ and $T(\mathbf{x}) > 1$ are then no longer available. Unfortunately, the inverse discharge problem, i.e. prediction of the residual charge distribution and field after a PD event, does not appear to be fundamentally solvable using the KT-model. In the future, it would clearly also be beneficial to extend the formulation to include accurate threshold values for K_c that include *a priori* calculations of the photoionization feedback region, rather than empirically obtaining this from experiments.

A salient feature our implementation of the $\hat{\text{Ito}}$ -KMC formulation is that it maintains the efficiency of an explicit time-stepping method, but it is not limited by a CFL time step restriction. Explicit fluid drift-diffusion codes, on the other hand, are typically CFL-limited everywhere. For example, for the void evolution in figure 10 there were no electrons in the void between 1 ns and 10 ns so that the $\hat{\text{Ito}}$ -KMC formulation could use time steps proportional to the ion drift time scale. However, in a fluid code the electron density would only asymptotically approach zero as the electrons drift toward the void surface, and an explicit fluid code would still be mandated to use a CFL-restricted time step to avoid growth of numerical instabilities. The flexible time step controls in the $\hat{\text{Ito}}$ -KMC formulation therefore permits us to run these types of simulations with far greater efficiency than what is possible in a fluid formulation.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at the following URL/DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14604982>.

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